

INTEGRATED GEOPHYSICAL RESEARCH ON THE ANCIENT AND MEDIEVAL FORTRESS LOCATED ON CAPE CHIRAKMAN, THE TOWN OF KAVARNA

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ABSTRACT. In this article we present geophysical investigation carried out with state-of-the-art equipment on the Antiquity and Middle Ages fortress located on Cape Chirakman, the town of Kavarna. A geomagnetic survey with high sensitivity potassium quantum magnetometer and a ground-penetrating radar survey with a 350 MHz wireless antenna were carried out. The retrieved results were integrated in a geographic information system environment and complemented with the archaeological documentation. The conducted research is an important source of information for the planning of future archeological research and site conservation on an archaeological site of high tourist, expositional, and scientific importance.

Key words: magnetic gradiometry, ground-penetrating radar (GPR), archaeological geophysics, fortress on Cape Chirakman.

ИНТЕГРИРАНИ ГЕОФИЗИЧНИ ИЗСЛЕДВАНИЯ НА АНТИЧНА И СРЕДНОВЕКОВНА КРЕПОСТ НА НОС ЧИРАКМАН, ГРАД КАВАРНА

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РЕЗЮМЕ. В тази статия са представени геофизичните изследвания, извършени със съвременен оборудване на територията на античната и средновековна крепост на нос Чиракман, гр. Каварна. Извършени са геомагнитно проучване с високо чувствителен калиев квантов магнитометър и георадарно проучване с 350 MHz безжична антена. Получените резултати са интегрирани в ГИС среда допълнени с археологическата документация. Направените изследвания са важен източник на информация при планирането на бъдещите археологически проучвания и теренната консервация на проучваният археологически обект с висока туристическа, експозиционна и научна стойност.

Ключови думи: магнитна градиометрия, георадар, археологическа геофизика, крепост на нос Чиракман.

Introduction

The Bizone archaeological site is located in the end of cape Chirakman, the town of Kavarna (Fig. 1). The earliest habitation remains unclear. The site probably reached its peak in the Hellenistic period. The earliest known mention of the name Bizone was in a decree from Histria in honor of Agathocles from 200 BC. A strong earthquake in the 1st century AD destroyed a large part of the city town. In the 6th century, the fortress was subjected to Avar-Slavic invasions. In the Middle Ages, the site was restored under the name of Karvuna.

Fig. 1. Regional map with location of the archaeological site

Most of the revealed structures are dwellings and stone buildings. (Bonev et al. 2022) Buildings from different periods often overlap and intersect, which makes the field research complex from an archaeological point of view. This requires careful planning of archaeological investigations (Milo et al., 2022; Tzankov et al., 2022; Malamidou et al., 2023), for which the present study was conducted.

For the geophysical survey, an area of around 5000 sq. m. between current excavation sectors was selected. Geomagnetic survey and ground penetrating radar (GPR) were chosen for this, being well-established methods providing speed for the magnetics (Becker, 2008; Tzankov et al., 2017) and possibility to retrieve depth information from GPR (Capizzi et al., 2007; Tsankov, 2023; Tsankov & Kisyov, 2015; Tzankov & Zidarov 2024).

Measurement techniques, methods and deliverables

Before the start of the geophysical works, the area for survey was prepared for work. Part of the plateau of Cape Chirakman was cleared of vegetation. Then, on the area prepared for measurement, a reference square grid of geodetic points was created with a northwest-southeast orientation, coinciding with that of regularly conducted archaeological excavations.

Geomagnetic survey

For the geomagnetic survey, a GSMP-25G potassium quantum gradiometer, with two magnetic sensors placed above each other and a differential GNSS (DGNSS) receiver for position tracking were used for measuring magnetic values along the profiles. A GSM-19W proton magnetometer was placed stationary in an area with a minimal vertical and horizontal gradient for a local magnetic base station.

The field survey was carried out in a zigzag motion along traverses with 1 m spacing between them. The profile lines were geodetically referenced to the BGS2005 cadastral coordinate system and to the local archeological network. Where possible, the profile lines for the geomagnetic survey were extended to maximise coverage, in which case the DGNSS receiver integrated in the magnetometer was used for positioning.

The vertical spacing between the two magnetic sensors was 1.54 m. Magnetic data (T_{rover}) was corrected for diurnal variation with data from the base station (T_{base}) with reference field value (datum) of $T_{ref} = 48\,650$ nT using the formula

$$T_{corr} = T_{rover} - T_{base} + T_{ref} \quad (1)$$

Based on the processed primary data and using grid generation software, grids with 0.5 x 0.5 m cell size were created. The following basic digital models of the geomagnetic field in UTM-35N projected coordinate system were generated:

- Map of the total magnetic intensity for the first level (Fig. 2);
- Map of the vertical gradient of the magnetic field (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Map of the total magnetic intensity in the studied area

Fig. 3. Map of the vertical magnetic gradient in the studied area

Ground penetrating radar survey

In order to improve the quality and informativeness of geomagnetic data and enhance the magnetic effect of hidden underground anthropogenic sources of different size and depth,

several common processing steps were followed and standard filters have been applied to the data. This included:

- Striping and displacement errors from zigzag motion and heading error were corrected with microleveling.
- A reduction to pole filter was applied to simplify the field through removing anomalies' distortions from inclination and declination of earth magnetic field.
- High-pass filters for removing anomalies with sizes larger, than 5, 10, and 20 m, as well as further anomalies shape, size, and location enhancement filters.

Georadar survey

For the GPR survey, a UtilityScan unit was used: a wireless, portable system using HyperStacking technology, ensuring high data quality, with an integrated LineTrac system, equipped with a central frequency 350HS antenna.

GPR data were processed using ReflexW software with the following main steps:

- Geometrisation, including setting coordinates, orientation, and alignment of the profiles.
- Basic processing by noise removal, signal gain adjustments, background removal, etc.
- Advanced processing involving predictive deconvolution to suppress reverberations, signal migration for accurate spatial representation, etc.

Velocity of electromagnetic waves in the subsurface was determined using hyperbola fitting and comparison with known reflectors.

Analysis and results

Geomagnetic data

Magnetic intensity is in the range of 48 613 – 48 677 nT (64 nT) with 80% in the range of 48 638.8 nT – 48 654.5 nT (16 nT). Vertical gradient is in the range of -15.33 – 13.29 nT/m with 80% in the range of -3.35 – 2.73 nT/m.

Fig. 4. Map of the total magnetic intensity in the studied area with anomalies bigger than 5 m removed (5 m size high-pass filter) with archaeological plans and outlined anomalies

Data was integrated in GIS environment with archaeological field data and plans, and visually analysed for anomalies from ancient activity based on shape, intensity, and correlation with excavated archaeological structures. Several anomalies that cannot be associated with surface shape, obstacles, and known modern activities causing distortion in the magnetic signal have been identified and outlined (Fig. 4 and Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Map of the vertical magnetic gradient in the studied area with archaeological plans and outlined anomalies

Magnetic anomalies were enhanced with palettes and colour ramps that improve outlines and visual perception (Fig. 6). High intensity anomalies that are identified can be produced from ferromagnetic archaeological structures, like fire pits and large pottery concentrations. Low magnetic linear anomalies can be associated with walls or concentrated stones with non-magnetic properties.

Fig. 6. Map of the of the total magnetic intensity with enhanced colour ramp for high values and anomaly outlines

Although several anomalies were outlined, they cannot be unequivocally associated with ancient activities and can be produced by modern activities, like undocumented trenches, old piles from excavations and geological sources; thus, they must be tested with field excavations.

Ground penetrating radar survey

GPR data was exported as radargrams (Fig. 7) and a 3D model of reflections was created (Bornik & Neubauer, 2022). From the model, several planar slices at different depths were created and inspected for anomalies that can be produced from ancient features (Fig. 8 and Fig. 9). Features with high reflectivity are expected from zones with significant dielectric difference between stone walls, bedrock foundation, cultural layers, and accommodating mediums. For electromagnetic wave velocity, a mean value of 0.011 m/ns was estimated. GPR signal is characterised with low permittivity and a maximum depth of investigation of 2 m was estimated. In general, only one meaningful anomaly (Fig. 10) can be extracted from the GPR data.

Fig. 7. Example of a radargram

Fig. 8. Example of a GPR slice at an estimated depth of 1 m

Fig. 9. Example of a GPR slice at an estimated depth of 0.5 m

Fig. 10. A GPR anomaly (yellow rectangle) at an estimated depth of 0.5 m and archaeological plan

The possible reasons for this can be mineral composition, high values of clay components in sediments, and a heterogeneous medium. A multi-frequency antenna and higher

profile density could return better results in further investigations.

Conclusions

In summary, a geophysical investigation on the archaeological site on Cape Chirakman, the town of Kavarna was conducted with the following results and conclusions:

- An area of 5000 sq. m was examined with magnetometry and magnetic gradiometry with 61 parallel profile lines with 1m spacing.
- An area of 3300 sq. m. was investigated with ground penetrating radar with parallel profile lines with 1m spacing and 4 perpendicular profiles.
- Geophysical data were processed and analysed. Digital maps of the magnetic field and electromagnetic wave reflections were produced.
- Archaeological field maps and plans were digitised and integrated with geophysical data aerial and terrestrial photogrammetric models in GIS environment for future use and excavation planning and analyses.
- On the retrieved geophysical data, multiple anomalies are visible that can be produced from ancient activities.
- Anomalies were marked as future research areas in the planning of the archeological investigations (Fig. 11).

Fig. 11. Magnetic anomalies (green lines) and GPR anomalies (yellow lines) integrated in GIS environment with archaeological plans and DEM

Although several anomalies were marked they do not all have closed contours or forms and must be tested for verification with different nondestructive or destructive methods. Retrieved information from further archaeological field data from testing of anomalies can be useful for further analysis and constraining geophysical data.

The integration of geomagnetic, GPR, and archaeological field data enabled the identification of multiple anomalies of potential archaeological significance. The study demonstrates the effectiveness and limitations of multi-method geophysical approaches for non-invasive investigation of complex archaeological landscapes.

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